

Instructional Supervision and Performance Evaluation: A Correlation of Factors

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the correlation between instructional supervision and performance evaluation in the Public Elementary Schools of Bayawan City Division. The survey was descriptive and correlational in nature. It utilized the percentage, mean, weighted mean, and spearman rank correlation coefficient. The study found out that the extent of implementation of instructional supervision as perceived by the experienced teachers was “very high” in terms of the following aspects:(a) concept and purpose of instructional supervision; (b) planning and preparations for instructional supervision; and (c) organization and implementation of instructional supervision; (d) dialogue and discussion in post-instructional supervision; and (e) satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision. Likewise, the extent of implementation of instructional supervision as perceived by the novice teachers was also “very high” based on how they rated their instructional supervisors in terms of the first three areas. In addition, a moderate relationship was found to exist between the teachers’ job performance evaluation and the extent of implementation of instructional supervision in the following aspects: (a) concept and purpose of instructional supervision; (b) planning and preparations for instructional supervision; and (c) satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision.

Keywords: Instructional Supervision, Job Performance Evaluation, Correlation Study

Introduction

The teachers’ instructional effectiveness is considered a key to achieve optimum gains in the teaching-learning process. In order to ensure this, teachers’ efficiency in the educational environment must be sustained as this is an important aspect that promotes student achievement and professional development. In support to this, supervision of teachers must be constant as this has been one of the most important functions of our educational system. As cited in Tyagi (2010), instructional supervision provides guidance, support and empowerment of teachers for their professional development in the teaching-learning process. Supervision provides teachers the support, knowledge and skills that enable them to succeed. Moreover, the quality of instructional supervision develops among teachers good perceptions and positive attitudes towards the practice (Choy, 2011). Hoffman and Tesfaw (2012) added that teachers were convinced on the need of instructional supervisory engagements. Teachers welcome supervision if it is done in the right spirit with the aim of improving the learning process. It is also regarded that the quality of supervision practice is a key factor in determining school success (Hamzah, 2013).

Kuizon and Reyes (2014) further noted that quality education depends on the extent of implementation of instructional supervision especially in the public elementary and secondary

schools as part of the duties and functions of instructional supervisors. In addition, Limon (2015) mentioned that instructional supervisors perform varied roles for the improvement and development of curriculum instruction. Instructional supervisors, both the internal and external to the school, are tasked to do supervisory works and carry out supervisory functions to help teachers improve learning conditions. As a result, there were improvements in the quality of instruction and academic performance in learning institutions. In this connection, Babalola and Hafsatu (2016) emphasized that the improvement of students' academic achievement is the measure of effective supervision.

In line with the abovementioned, this study was designed to examine the Extent of Implementation of Instructional Supervision as perceived by the Novice and Experienced Teachers of the Department of Education-Bayawan City Division. It also revealed the correlation between factors such as teachers' perceptions and job performance evaluation.

Research Design

The study used the descriptive and correlational method of research in the sense that the extent of implementation of instructional supervision was surveyed and the results were related to teachers' job performance evaluation results.

Research Environment

The locale of the study is the public elementary schools of Bayawan City Division. Generally, the public elementary schools of Bayawan City Division are assigned with elementary school principals, head teachers, and teachers-in-charge who served as both school administrators and school-based supervisors. In addition, the division is administered and headed by a Schools Division Superintendent with the assistance of the Assistant Schools Division Superintendent, Curriculum Implementation Division Chief Supervisor, Division Education Program Supervisors, and Public Schools District Supervisors who used to constantly monitor the public elementary and secondary schools especially in the area of curriculum implementation and teaching instruction.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 70 novice teachers and 230 experienced teachers of the 30 public elementary schools of Bayawan City Division.

Research Instruments

The researcher used self-made questionnaires which were organized into three parts. Part one contained the profile of the teachers both the novice and experienced. Part two sought the data on the extent of implementation of instructional supervision. Part three was designed to seek data on the connection between the perceived extent of implementation of instructional supervision and job performance evaluation. The researcher-made questionnaire was constructed after a careful and thorough reading of books, articles, journals and electronic sources related to the topic. The modifications of the survey instrument were based on the review of related literature and the specific context of the study.

Research Procedure

A written letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Bayawan City requesting permission to allow the researcher to conduct the study on the different public elementary schools. Upon the approval of the request, copies of the approved letter have been given to the teachers-in-charge, head teachers and school principals of the participating schools to allow the researcher to administer the questionnaire to the identified novice and experienced teachers and to have access on their official records. The research instruments were retrieved as soon as the respondents have answered all the required information.

Findings

Table 1. Length of Teaching Experience of the Teachers

Number of Years	F	%
1 – 2	70	23.33
3 – 4	47	15.67
5 – 6	25	8.33
7 – 8	27	9.00
9 – 10	37	12.33
11 – 12	28	9.34
13 and above	66	22.00
Total	300	100.00

Table 1 indicates that 23.33% of the teachers have been in the service for 1-2 years referred to as novice teachers while 76.67% are teachers who have three or more years of working experience that ranges from 3-4 years and additional categories leading up to teaching experience of more than 13 years then considered as experienced teachers. Teaching experience in the classroom does matter. As what Gardner (2013) emphasized, experience is considered as the most important factor in predicting effectiveness. It also plays several important roles in education policies. Experienced is believed to bridge the gap between theory and practice as cited in Mariñas (2013). The variant core idea of “long years of teaching” as conceived to be a manifestation of an effective teaching echoed one of the findings that teaching experience had a positive effect on teacher effectiveness (Abulon,2014).

Table 2. Highest Educational Attainment of the Teachers

Number of Years	F	%
Bachelor’s Degree	100	33.33
With MA units	178	59.34
With MA	19	6.33
With Doctoral units	1	0.33
With Doctoral degree	2	0.67
Total	300	100.00

Table 2 shows that 33.33% of the teachers are bachelor degree holders and 59.34% are teachers with master’s degree units. However, only 6.33% have been found to complete an MA and 1.00% pursued doctoral studies. It is apparent in the findings that most of the teachers have only master’s degree units and only few of them are full-fledge master degree holders or have pursue further doctoral studies. This finding is supported by Mariñas (2013), Secong (2014), and Pescuela (2015) that most of the teachers pursue further studies to improve their craft, however only few of them were predicted to finish their degrees. In public schools, teachers are encouraged to finish completely their postgraduate studies as professional career advancement is one of the major requirements for promotion to higher position in educational agencies and higher salary rate for increased job responsibilities in addition to the enhancement of teacher’s theoretical and technical knowledge. As cited in Mariñas (2013), professional teacher development is a recommended method to improvement of not only skill, but performance in the classroom environment as well. It also establishes expert teachers and increases their job opportunities in addition to the benefits it will bring to their learners. Schools need highly qualified, expert teachers to improve the quality of education, and an advanced degree tells a school you are valuable, knowledgeable teacher that will have most impact on your students (Rosier, 2016).

Table 3. Teaching Position Held of the Teachers

Number of Years	F	%
Teacher I	191	63.67
Teacher II	70	23.34
Teacher III	37	12.33
Master Teacher I	1	0.33
Master Teacher II	1	0.33
Total	300	100.00

The findings in Table 3 reveal that majority of the teachers are in Teacher I positions representing 63.67%. The data imply that longer teaching experience and higher educational attainment come together as major requirements for promotion to higher position in educational agencies. Advance degree in teaching incorporate experience (Fushell & Tucker, 2013). Even 76.67% are considered experienced teachers and 66.67% pursue post-graduate studies as reflected in the previous tables, the combination of number of years of working experience and advancement of career opportunities really matter and make a difference. In affirmation, many occupations recognize employees' years of experience as a relevant factor in human resource policies, including compensation systems, benefits packages, and promotion decisions (Rice, 2010). The idea is that experience, gained over time, enhances the knowledge, skills, and productivity of workers. Moreover, education is a lifelong career. Teachers must use knowledge and skills in making strategic career choices. Fushell and Tucker (2013) found out that teachers undertake lifelong programs for different reasons, primarily to become a greater educator and to receive a salary increase. In addition, teachers must finished master's degree to improve their professional qualities and personal attributes (Secong, 2014). Furthermore, through experience, effectiveness and efficiency on the system were improved and developed (Torres, 2015).

Table 4. Instructional Supervision in Terms of Concept and Purpose

Indicators	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers		
	W X	VD	Equiva- lent	W X	VD	Equiva- lent
a. Concept of Instructional Supervision <i>Instructional Supervision is ...</i>	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers		
1 a model of a collaborative classroom instruction	4.56	SA	VH	4.29	SA	VH
2 a tool to promote shared instructional decisions	4.51	SA	VH	4.30	SA	VH
3 a means to define the roles of teachers in teaching instruction	4.58	SA	VH	4.34	SA	VH
4 a mechanism to provide instructional directions	4.56	SA	VH	4.39	SA	VH
5 an avenue for situational approach of instructional supervision	4.55	SA	VH	4.34	SA	VH
Composite	4.55	SA	VH	4.33	SA	VH
b. Purpose of Instructional Supervision <i>Instructional Supervision ...</i>	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers		
1 promotes cooperative work among instructional leaders and classroom teachers	4.60	SA	VH	4.41	SA	VH
2 improves instructional practices, student achievement and classroom management	4.58	SA	VH	4.43	SA	VH
3 considers the specific needs and developmental stages of individual teachers	4.54	SA	VH	4.36	SA	VH
4 focuses on teacher's knowledge, skills and ability towards curriculum improvement and staff development	4.51	SA	VH	4.31	SA	VH
5 analyses and makes judgments about teacher's instructional efficiency and effectiveness	4.44	SA	VH	4.34	SA	VH
Composite	4.54	SA	VH	4.37	SA	VH
Overall	4.55	SA	VH	4.35	SA	VH

Legend: Scale

4.21 – 5.00
3.41 – 4.20
2.61 – 3.40
1.81 – 2.60
1.00 – 1.80

Verbal Description

Strongly Agree (SA)
Agree (A)
Moderately Agree (MA)
Disagree (D)
Strongly Disagree (SD)

Equivalent (Extent of Implementation)

Very High (VH)
High (H)
Moderate (M)
Low (L)
Very Low (VL)

As shown in Table 4, there is a “very high” extent of implementation of instructional supervision as perceived by both of the novice and experienced teachers in the aspect of concept and purpose of instructional supervision. This implies that both categories of teachers demonstrate greater understanding and display higher awareness on the significance of the conduct of instructional supervision as a tool for teacher’s growth.

Instructional supervision is very important to the development of education and it is fitting to establish how it is perceived by teachers in schools. Unless teachers perceive supervision as a process of improving learning conditions and promoting professional growth, the supervisory exercise will not achieve its desired purpose. Researchers also attached numerous purposes to instructional supervision: improving classroom instruction, providing specific direction, fostering curriculum innovations, improving performance evaluation, encouraging human relations and supporting collaboration (Payne, 2010; Awuah, 2011; Wanzare, 2012).

The result shown in the table is in conjunction to the study of Kuizon and Reyes (2014) that collaborative approach to supervision is mostly favoured by instructional supervisors. Moreover, the findings in the study of Hoffman and Tesfaw (2012) show that both beginner and experienced teachers were convinced of the need for instructional supervision, and believe that every teacher can benefit from instructional supervision. Teachers also welcome supervision if it is done in the right spirit and with the aim of improving the learning process and promoting teacher growth. Finally, Tshabalala (2013) found out that teachers generally perceive classroom instructional supervision in a positive way. They are aware of what it is and appreciated its purpose.

Table 5. Instructional Supervision in Terms of Planning and Preparations

Indicators	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers		
	WX	VD	Equiva-lent	WX	VD	Equiva-lent
a. Advance Notifications and Planning Lessons with Supervisors <i>Instructional Supervisor ...</i>	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers		
1 keeps teachers aware of the conduct of instructional supervision	4.53	SA	VH	4.29	SA	VH
2 notifies teachers of classroom visitations and lesson observations	4.46	SA	VH	4.21	SA	VH
3 sets up specific sessions with the teachers to discuss curriculum implementation	4.44	SA	VH	4.21	SA	VH
4 provides teachers with adequate information to become familiar with supervision of instruction	4.47	SA	VH	4.31	SA	VH
5 involves teachers in the planning and preparation of the delivery of classroom lessons	4.50	SA	VH	4.33	SA	VH
Composite	4.48	SA	VH	4.27	SA	VH
b. Informal Visitations and Classroom Observations <i>Instructional Supervisor ...</i>						
1 informally visits teachers in their respective classes during teaching instruction	4.29	SA	VH	3.93	A	VH
2 monitors teachers outside the classroom during real-world lesson application	4.21	SA	VH	3.93	A	VH
3 supervise teachers on a regular basis inside the classroom during curriculum implementation	4.31	SA	VH	3.94	A	VH
4 enters the classroom as unobtrusively as possible in the conduct of lesson observations	4.22	SA	VH	3.91	A	VH
5 capitalize the expertise of teachers to share supervisory knowledge, skills and information	4.32	SA	VH	4.09	A	VH
Composite	4.27	SA	VH	3.96	A	VH
Overall	4.38	SA	VH	4.12	A	VH

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Equivalent (Extent of Implementation)
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 5 signifies that there is a higher extent of implementation of instructional supervision as perceived by the experienced teachers compared to the novice teachers in the aspect of planning and preparations for instructional supervision.

In affirmation to advance notifications and planning lessons with supervisors, arrangements should be made in advance for the formal classroom observation. Most teachers prefer the supervisor to notify them of the visit so that they can prepare their lessons. Pansiri's (2008) study indicated that their supervisors planned class visits with them rather than the school head determined when visits would be conducted without consulting with teachers. Hence, careful planning by the supervisor should precede a classroom visit. Awuah (2011) also revealed that teachers want to be involved in pre-observation planning. However, experienced teachers' higher perceived extent of implementation of this aspect of instructional supervision than the novice teachers can be attributed to the number of years in service. As cited in Mariñas (2013), though adequately trained, the new teachers may be at greater risks for failure than the experienced teachers for not having yet acquired skills necessary like classroom management and instructional skills that can only be acquired through experience. This is supported by the study of Faltado and Faltado (2014) which stated that there is a significant difference in the needs of novice teachers when grouped by work experience. In line with this, Kadlong and Usop (2013) added that new teachers need support and development to improve their knowledge, practices and skills.

It is recommended to have actual planning and preparation of the lessons with supervisor. Furthermore, supervisors should mutually decide with their teachers on what and how to observe before proceeding to the classroom to observe a lesson.

Table 6. Instructional Supervision in Terms of Organization and Implementation

Indicators	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers		
	WX	VD	Equivalent	WX	VD	Equivalent
a. Lesson Plan Review						
<i>Instructional supervisor examines teacher's ...</i>						
1	4.52	SA	VH	4.34	SA	VH
2	4.51	SA	VH	4.30	SA	VH
3	4.51	SA	VH	4.30	SA	VH
4	4.48	SA	VH	4.26	SA	VH
5	4.58	SA	VH	4.33	SA	VH
6	4.52	SA	VH	4.33	SA	VH
7	4.53	SA	VH	4.21	SA	VH
8	4.49	SA	VH	4.26	SA	VH
9	4.55	SA	VH	4.21	SA	VH
10	4.56	SA	VH	4.31	SA	VH
Composite	4.52	SA	VH	4.28	SA	VH
b. Actual Classroom Observation						
<i>Instructional supervisor examines teacher's</i>						
1	4.67	SA	VH	4.36	SA	VH
2	4.65	SA	VH	4.24	SA	VH
3	4.64	SA	VH	4.30	SA	VH
4	4.63	SA	VH	4.27	SA	VH
5	4.62	SA	VH	4.33	SA	VH
Composite	4.64	SA	VH	4.30	SA	VH
Overall	4.58	SA	VH	4.29	SA	VH

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Equivalent (Extent of Implementation)
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

As indicated in Table 6, both categories of teachers perceived “very high” extent of implementation for actual classroom observation in the aspect of organization and implementation of instructional supervision.

Lesson observation is one of the major functions of supervisors. It has been seen as a major tool that supervisors use to assess the content knowledge of teachers and their competency in instructional strategies and practices so as to provide the necessary assistance to improve instruction. Babalola and Hafsatu (2016) therefore noted that administrators should ensure that teachers prepare lesson notes prior to curricular implementation.

In the conduct of classroom observation, Afolabi and Loto (2008) identified, among others, the following areas: the nature of lesson plan, lesson presentation and reference materials. Foremost, the lesson plan is a reflection of the level of preparedness as well as the effort the teacher made in gathering information for the lesson. Thus, the school head must critically examine the following items of the lesson plan: the clarity and appropriateness of the learner behavioural objectives, the relevance and adequacy of the lesson notes, selection of appropriate teaching aids, and selection of appropriate evaluation techniques to determine the extent of realizing the objective effectively as cited from Edo Journal of Counselling Vol. 2, No. 2, 2009. In addition, Payne (2010) said that classroom observation is an opportunity to gain insight from colleagues and administrators through purposeful observation.

Table 7. Instructional Supervision in Terms of Dialogue and Discussion

Indicators	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers			
	WX	VD	Equivalent	WX	VD	Equivalent	
a. Immediacy of Feedback on Classroom Observation							
<i>Instructional supervisor ...</i>							
1	conducts supervisory conferences right after observing teachers	4.57	SA	VH	4.24	SA	VH
2	provides immediate feedback after the teaching-learning process	4.57	SA	VH	4.24	SA	VH
3	spends enough time to discuss teacher's strengths and capabilities	4.49	SA	VH	4.13	A	H
4	gives sufficient time to discuss teacher's weaknesses and difficulties	4.49	SA	VH	4.17	A	H
5	allots time to share supervisory experiences through constructive dialogue, mutual trust and shared expertise	4.49	SA	VH	4.19	A	H
	Composite	4.52	SA	VH	4.19	A	H
b. Adequacy of Feedback on Instructional Supervision							
<i>Instructional supervisor ...</i>							
1	provides data-based feedback and responses	4.45	SA	VH	4.17	A	H
2	gives appreciation and positive comments	4.53	SA	VH	4.26	SA	VH
3	discusses teacher's weaknesses and difficulties	4.46	SA	VH	4.24	SA	VH
4	promotes two-way communication process	4.48	SA	VH	4.24	SA	VH
5	supports curriculum and staff development	4.49	SA	VH	4.23	SA	VH
	Composite	4.48	SA	VH	4.23	SA	VH
	Overall	4.50	SA	VH	4.21	SA	VH

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Equivalent (Extent of Implementation)
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 7 presents that there is a “very high” extent of implementation as perceived by both of the novice and experienced teachers in the areas of immediacy of feedback on classroom observation and adequacy of feedback on instructional supervision in the aspect of dialogue and discussion in post-instructional supervision.

Proponents of instructional supervision consider post-conference in which feedback is given in supervision as an instructional dialogue. The idea of providing feedback after supervision is considered significant as it solely involves both parties sharing what was observed and experienced during supervision. According to Hunsaker and Johanna (2009),

improving employees' performance depends on balanced and considerate feedback. Feedback is regarded as a performance motivator as it involves provision of information on progress towards accomplishing a goal, or data indicating where the shortfall occurs. Hattie (2009) contends that providing constructive feedback to teachers based on the meaningful appraisal of their work has consistently been shown to produce significant improvements on teaching and learning on classrooms.

The results on the immediacy of feedback of classroom observation is in conjunction with the findings of Tshabalala (2013) that teachers preferred immediate post supervision. On the other hand, on the adequacy of feedback on instructional supervision, the results was supported by Amina (2015) who said that there was also feedback in the form of reports and queries to teachers on their performances as well as organized personal meetings with teachers to discuss their shortcomings on lesson notes preparation, class attendance, and report to school. Therefore, as an instructional source, supervisors provide, not only a diagnosis of teaching, but also feedback that enables teacher's professional growth and development. Mariñas (2013) said that school heads need to establish a positive work climate. This phase has a significant bearing on the success of supervision and requires qualities like intimacy, honesty, tactfulness, considerateness alongside mutual understanding from both parties. Exchange of ideas leads to teachers' improvement when issues discussed are educational and beneficial most especially pertaining to classroom practice or management (Torres, 2015).

Table 8. Instructional Supervision in Terms of Satisfaction and Evaluation (Part A)

Indicators	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers		
	$\bar{W\bar{X}}$	VD	Equi-valent	$\bar{W\bar{X}}$	VD	Equi-valent
Satisfaction with Instructional Supervision						
As a supervisee, I am satisfied with the following:						
<i>a. Instructional Supervisory Practices based on the ...</i>						
1	overall quality of instructional supervision	4.40	SA	VH	4.14	A H
2	general organization of instructional supervision	4.36	SA	VH	4.16	A H
3	administrative support to instructional supervision	4.36	SA	VH	4.09	A H
4	objective evaluation of instructional supervision	4.37	SA	VH	4.16	A H
5	cooperative action in instructional supervision	4.34	SA	VH	4.03	A H
	Composite	4.37	SA	VH	4.11	A H
<i>b. Instructional Supervisor's ...</i>						
1	planning skills on observing, monitoring and evaluating the instructional process	4.37	SA	VH	4.04	A H
2	analytical skills to explain the relationship that exist between teaching and learning	4.36	SA	VH	4.00	A H
3	social competence in building collaborative and empowering relationships	4.34	SA	VH	4.10	A H
4	communicative competence on holding one-on-one conferences with teachers	4.33	SA	VH	4.03	A H
5	creative and innovative skills in dealing with complex classroom practices	4.34	SA	VH	4.01	A H
	Composite	4.35	SA	VH	4.04	A H
Legend: Scale		Verbal Description		Equivalent (Extent of Implementation)		
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	(SA)	Very High	(VH)	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	(A)	High	(H)	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	(MA)	Moderate	(M)	
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	(D)	Low	(L)	
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	(SD)	Very Low	(VL)	

Table 8 displays a higher extent of implementation based on the experienced teachers' perceptions compared to that of the novice in the area of satisfaction with instructional supervisory practices and instructional supervisors' skills. In turn, Zepeda (2007) revealed that the satisfaction of teachers depends largely on the availability of supervisory choices based on their needs. Peplinski (2009) further noted about the utilization of differentiated supervision based mainly on a teacher's years of experience and his or her need of such strategies.

In line with this, a research conducted indicated that beginning teachers have desired more on the frequent use of instructional supervision that meets their professional needs, promotes trust and collaboration, and gives them support, advise, and help (Choy, Chong, Wong & Wong, 2011).

Table 9. Instructional Supervision in Terms of Satisfaction and Evaluation (Part B)

Indicators	\bar{w}	VD	Equi- valent	\bar{w}	VD	Equi- valent
	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers		
1. Evaluation of Instructional Supervision						
a. Based on my observation, the instructional supervisor accomplishes the appraisal forms through:						
1	conducting lesson plan reviews	4.46	SA	VH	4.17	A H
2	performing classroom observations	4.46	SA	VH	4.16	A H
3	examining classroom discipline or management	4.47	SA	VH	4.10	A H
4	checking the routine management	4.47	SA	VH	4.10	A H
5	monitoring the record management	4.48	SA	VH	4.14	A H
	Composite	4.47	SA	VH	4.13	A H
b. Based on my observation, the instructional supervisor prepares the supervisory reports through:						
1	accomplishing the form 178 upon the observation of the teaching-learning process	4.57	SA	VH	4.26	SA VH
2	monitoring the class targets or accomplishments	4.52	SA	VH	4.22	SA VH
3	reviewing IPCRF as part of performance monitoring and tracking	4.50	SA	VH	4.22	SA VH
4	keeping the appraisal forms for record management and future reference	4.48	SA	VH	4.23	SA VH
5	assessing the realization of government's instructional policies and practices	4.50	SA	VH	4.17	A H
	Composite	4.51	SA	VH	4.22	SA VH
	Overall	4.23	SA	VH	4.13	A H
Legend: Scale						
	4.21 – 5.00	Verbal Description		Equivalent (Extent of Implementation)		
	3.41 – 4.20	Strongly Agree (SA)		Very High (VH)		
	2.61 – 3.40	Agree (A)		High (H)		
	1.81 – 2.60	Moderately Agree (MA)		Moderate (M)		
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree (D)		Low (L)		
		Strongly Disagree (SD)		Very Low (VL)		

Table 9 signifies that experienced teachers perceived a higher extent of implementation of instructional supervision compared to novice teachers on the accomplishment of appraisal forms. Education requires supervision of classroom instruction to evaluate teacher's effectiveness. This generally involves an administrator observing and evaluating lessons in a classroom, documenting the teacher's performance, and sharing suggestions for improvement (Zepeda, 2007; Farley, 2010; Shohet, 2011; Weld, 2012). Hoffman and Tesfaw (2012) noted that supervisory choices should be available to beginner teachers. Supervisors should employ various supervisory options by selecting and coordinating these tools focusing on the individual teacher's needs and problems and the issues of teaching and learning that can enhance teachers' professional development and improve their instructional efficiency (Hussen, 2015).

Table 10. Summary Table on the Extent of Implementation of Instructional Supervision

Variables	Experienced Teachers			Novice Teachers		
	WX	VD	Equivalent	WX	VD	Equivalent
A Concept and Purpose	4.55	SA	VH	4.35	SA	VH
B Planning and Preparations	4.38	SA	VH	4.12	A	VH
C Organization and Implementation	4.58	SA	VH	4.29	SA	VH
D Dialogue and Discussion	4.50	SA	VH	4.21	SA	VH
E Satisfaction and Evaluation	4.23	SA	VH	4.13	A	VH
Overall	4.45	SA	VH	4.22	SA	VH

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Equivalent (Extent of Implementation)
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 10 discloses that both the experienced and novice teachers have “very high” level of agreement on the extent of implementation of instructional supervision on the following aspects: concept and purpose of instructional supervision, organization and implementation of instructional supervision, and dialogue and discussion in post-instructional supervision. However, differences are noted in the planning and preparations for instruction supervision as well as satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision. This can be attributed to teachers’ confidence level to share knowledge, skills and expertise in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of the delivery of the subject matter as part of the instructional process. In turn, Powers (2012) indicates that new teachers felt only somewhat prepared or not well-prepared in the area of lesson planning, instructional strategies, and classroom management.

A number of studies also revealed that the beginning years of teaching experience are crucial to the development of novice teachers. In line with this, the study of Choy (2013) found out that teacher’s pedagogical knowledge and skills continue to develop and increase significantly in the first three years. Hence, beginning teachers in their novice years of teaching would like to receive more training which could be used to better meet their professional developmental need (Rees, 2015).

Table 11. Job Performance of Novice and Experienced Public School Teachers

Rating	Experienced Teachers		Novice Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
4.500 – 5.000 (Outstanding)	124	53.91	4	5.71
3.500– 4.499 (Very Satisfactory)	103	44.78	6	94.29
2.500 – 3.499 (Satisfactory)	3	1.31		
Total	230	100.00	7	100.00
Overall Rating	4.470 (Very Satisfactory)		4.110 (Very Satisfactory)	

Table 11 exhibits the job performance of the novice and experienced public elementary school teachers. It reveals that 53.91% of the experienced teachers have a performance of 4.500 and above compared to only 5.71% of the novice teachers with outstanding rating. Moreover, 44.78% of the experienced teachers have ratings of 3.500--4.499 while 94.29% of

the novice teachers have very satisfactory rating. The data also reveal that both categories of teachers are at very satisfactory level with 4.470 for experienced and 4.110 for novice teachers. This means that the teachers have displayed effectiveness, efficiency, and timeliness in doing their teaching duties most especially relating to the different Key Result Areas: Teaching and Learning Process, Pupils Outcomes, Community Involvement and Professional Growth and Development. Moreover, the finding is supported by Secong (2014), Pescuela (2015), and Torres(2015) which all revealed that almost all of the teachers have a “very satisfactory” rating as shown in their performance evaluation system. Teacher performance varies at all levels of experience. Teachers’ effectiveness is associated with experience and most steep on teachers’ initial years but continues to be significant as teachers reach the second, and often third, decades of their careers (Kini & Podolsky, 2016).

Table 12. Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Instructional Supervision as Perceived by the Teachers when They are Grouped According to Their Profile

Variables	Length of Teaching Experience		Teaching Position Held		Highest Educational Attainment	
	Novice (1-2 yrs)	Experienced (3yrs. & above)	Teacher I	Teacher II /III/MT	Baccalaureate Degree	With MA units/ Degree/ with EdD units/ Degree
A. Concept and Purpose of Instructional Supervision	4.35 (Very High)	4.54 (Very High)	4.51 (Very High)	4.48 (Very High)	4.34 (Very High)	4.58 (Very High)
B. Planning and Preparations for Instruction Supervision	4.12 (High)	4.38 (Very High)	4.30 (Very High)	4.34 (Very High)	4.21 (Very High)	4.37 (Very High)
C. Organization and Implementation of Instructional Supervision	4.29 (Very High)	4.56 (Very High)	4.48 (Very High)	4.52 (Very High)	4.36 (Very High)	4.57 (Very High)
D. Dialogue and Discussion in Post-Instructional Supervision	4.21 (Very High)	4.50 (Very High)	4.22 (Very High)	4.46 (Very High)	4.36 (Very High)	4.47 (Very High)
E. Satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision	4.13 (High)	4.42 (Very High)	4.32 (Very High)	4.41 (Very High)	4.20 (High)	4.43 (Very High)
Overall	4.22	4.48	4.41	4.44	4.29	4.48

Table 12 reflects the difference in the extent of implementation of instructional supervision as perceived by the teachers when they are grouped according to their profiles: length of teaching experience, teaching position held, and highest educational attainment.

For the length of teaching experience, the table reveals a “very high” extent of implementation of instructional supervision on most of the aspects as perceived by both novice and experienced teachers except for the planning and preparations for instruction supervision as well as satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision.

The teachers with 1-2 years of working experience still rely on their pre-service teaching experiences, student-teaching engagements, and field study courses in college years. Hence, they have limited knowledge, skills or content expertise to be shared with various instructional

leaders in the conduct of planning and preparations for instructional supervisory process. In line with this, Faltado and Faltado (2014) suggest that novice teachers may be prioritized to attend seminars, trainings or workshops as they are in much need of more knowledge and skills. The experienced teachers, on the other hand, can attribute their higher level of agreement on the knowledge, skills, and expertise that they accumulated in the passage of years. They have richer knowledge to draw from and can contribute insights and ideas to the course of teaching and learning process and engagements (Kosgei, 2013).

However, there is no difference in the profile of teachers on teaching position held which imply that whatever the teaching position, all teachers assume the same teaching responsibilities, duties, and functions. Awuah (2011) noted that teachers are aware of the duties they are expected to perform. In affirmation, the study of Pescuela (2015) and Torres (2015) implied that teachers know their personal responsibilities, rights, and functions. They were already responsible to implement the curriculum.

On the other hand, both of the novice and experienced teachers have similar perceived extent of implementation on most of the aspects of instructional supervision when they are grouped according to highest educational attainment except for satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision. This can be attributed to longer years of teaching experience and higher educational attainment as what have also reflected in the planning and preparation for instructional supervision aspect.

Table 13. Job Performance of Novice and Experienced Public School Teachers

Variables Being Paired with Teachers' Job Performance	Computed r_s	Degree of Relationship
A. Concept and Purpose of Instructional Supervision	0.311	Moderate
B. Planning and Preparations for Instruction Supervision	0.309	Moderate
C. Organization and Implementation of Instructional Supervision	0.279	Weak
D. Dialogue and Discussion in Post-Instructional Supervision	0.273	Weak
E. Satisfaction with and Evaluation of Instructional Supervision	0.322	Moderate
Overall	0.343	Moderate

Legend:	Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
	Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00	- strong relationship
	Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49	- moderate relationship
	Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29	- weak relationship
	Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09	- very weak relationship

Table 13 presents that the extent of implementation of instructional supervision on the following aspects: concept and purpose of instructional supervision, planning and preparations for instructional supervision, and satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision are moderately related to teachers' job performance. This means that the higher the perceived extent of implementation of instructional supervision on the mentioned variables, the higher also the teachers' rating in the performance job evaluation result. The positive correlation further means that the perceived extent of implementation of instructional supervision on the abovementioned variables is directly proportional with job performance evaluation.

The findings of Mariñas (2013) conform to this as she noted that there is a significant relationship between the extent of principals' manifestations of leadership behaviour and extent

of teachers' empowerment in terms of human relations and instructional leadership domains. Tshabalala (2013) also found out that teachers generally perceive classroom instructional supervision in a positive way. Moreover, the study of Mahad (2014) revealed that with respect to teachers' attitude, majority of the respondents expressed positive attitude towards supervisory practices, however, experienced teachers had shown higher level of agreement on overall the attitude related items in the survey.

In addition, the study confirmed that teachers' attitude toward supervisory practices has a weak, positive and significant correlation with their perceptions of actual supervision, and moderate, positive correlation with their perception of ideal supervisory approaches. Furthermore, school administrators' implementation of instructional leadership in terms of managing the entire instructional program giving focus on supervising and evaluating instruction, coordinating the curriculum, and monitoring school progress is perceived to be "very high" by the teachers, hence, having a significant relationship with their job performance (Pescuela, 2015).

Torres (2015) further noted that the administrative and leadership behaviour of elementary school principals and leadership behaviours in the areas of person orientation and system orientation were "very high" in the same manner with that of evaluation of teachers' performances, leadership roles and enhancement of teachers' competence, thus, is significantly related to the performance of teachers.

On the other hand, the rest of the variables like the organization and implementation of instructional supervision as well as the dialogue and discussion in post-instructional supervision have a weak relationship with their job performance evaluation results. This means that those variables are not strong predictors/determinants of the teachers' job performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are hereby drawn:

1. Three-fourths of the teachers were considered experienced. Most of them earned master's degree units and were classified as Teacher I in their position held.
2. The extent of implementation of instructional supervision as perceived by the experienced teachers was "very high" in terms of the following aspects: (a) concept and purpose of instructional supervision; (b) planning and preparations for instructional supervision; (c) organization and implementation of instructional supervision; (d) dialogue and discussion in post-instructional supervision; and (e) satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision. Likewise, the extent of implementation of instructional supervision as perceived by the novice teachers was also "very high" based on how they rated their instructional supervisors in the following aspects: (a) concept and purpose of instructional supervision; (b) organization and implementation of instructional supervision; and (c) dialogue and discussion in post-instructional supervision.
3. The teaching job performance of both the novice and experienced public elementary school teachers was in a "very satisfactory" level.
4. There was a difference in the perception on the extent of implementation of instructional supervision in the following aspects when teachers are grouped as novice and experienced

teachers in favor of the latter: (a) planning and preparations for instructional supervision; and (b) satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision. A difference had also occurred in the extent of implementation of instructional supervision in the aspect of satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision when teachers were grouped as baccalaureate degree holders and with master's units/ degrees or with doctoral units/ degrees in favor of the latter.

5. A moderate relationship was found to exist between the extent of implementation of instructional supervision: (a) concept and purpose of instructional supervision; (b) planning and preparations for instructional supervision; and (c) satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision and teachers' job performance evaluation.

In general, the extent of implementation of instructional supervision as perceived by the novice and experienced teachers is "very high" and has a moderate relationship to teachers' job performance.

Recommendations

On the bases of the findings and conclusions drawn, the followings are recommended:

1. Teachers are encouraged to finish master's degrees and even pursue doctoral studies as professional career advancement incorporated with number of years of working experience afford them greater theoretical and pedagogical knowledge, higher salary rate, and higher position in the education department.
2. Since experienced teachers have higher perceived extent of implementation of instructional supervision in the aspects of planning and preparations for instructional supervision as well as satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision due to their longer years of working experience, they must make it a point that novice teachers will be assisted by lending them instructional materials, modules, budget of work, and other resources needed in the pre-observation planning process and post-instructional supervision conferences.
3. As novice teachers wanted more time to engage in reflective and collaborative approaches to supervision, there is a need for both the instructional supervisors and experienced teachers to address their professional developmental needs to improve their knowledge, practices, and skills.
4. As majority of the experienced teachers pursue post-graduate studies and some of the novice teachers have only master's degree units or still have bachelor degrees, novice teachers may be prioritized to attend seminars, workshops, and trainings to increase knowledge, skills, and expertise on the instructional process, lesson planning, and classroom management among others.
5. Since majority of the items on satisfaction with and evaluation of instructional supervision aspect have higher extent of implementation as perceived by experienced teachers, instructional leaders should provide novice teachers specific instruction and constant monitoring as well as give them initial direction and undivided attention as what situational leadership theory suggests.

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Appendix A

Survey Instrument

Instructional Supervision and Performance Evaluation: A Correlation of Factors

Direction: Please indicate the extent of implementation of instructional supervision using the following scale:

Verbal Description	Explanation
Strongly Agree	The degree to which the teacher agrees with the statement is 81-100%.
Agree	The degree to which the teacher agrees with the statement is 61-80%.
Moderately Agree	The degree to which the teacher agrees with the statement is 41-60%.
Disagree	The degree to which the teacher agrees with the statement is 21-40%.
Strongly Disagree	The degree to which the teacher agrees with the statement is 1-20%.

A. Concept and Purpose of Instructional Supervision

Indicators	Strongly Agree	Agree	Moderately Agree	Dis-agree	Strongly Disagree
a. Concept of Instructional Supervision					
<i>Instructional Supervision is ...</i>					
1 a model of a collaborative classroom instruction					
2 a tool to promote shared instructional decisions					
3 a means to define the roles of teachers in teaching instruction					
4 a mechanism to provide instructional directions					
5 an avenue for situational approach of instructional supervision					
b. Purpose of Instructional Supervision					
<i>Instructional Supervision ...</i>					
1 promotes cooperative work among instructional leaders and classroom teachers					
2 improves instructional practices, student achievement and classroom management					
3 considers the specific needs and developmental stages of individual teachers					
4 focuses on teacher's knowledge, skills and ability towards curriculum improvement and staff development					
5 analyses and makes judgments about teacher's instructional efficiency and effectiveness					

B. Planning and Preparations for Instructional Supervision

Indicators	Strongly Agree	Agree	Moderately Agree	Dis-agree	Strongly Disagree
a. Advance Notifications and Planning Lessons with Supervisors					
<i>Instructional Supervisor ...</i>					
1 keeps teachers aware of the conduct of instructional supervision					
2 notifies teachers of classroom visitations and lesson observations					
3 sets up specific sessions with the teachers to discuss curriculum implementation					
4 provides teachers with adequate information to become familiar with supervision of instruction					
5 involves teachers in the planning and preparation of the delivery of classroom lessons					
b. Informal Visitations and Classroom Observations					
<i>Instructional Supervisor ...</i>					
1 informally visits teachers in their respective classes during teaching instruction					
2 monitors teachers outside the classroom during real-world lesson application					
3 supervise teachers on a regular basis inside the classroom during curriculum implementation					
4 enters the classroom as unobtrusively as possible in the conduct of lesson observations					
5 capitalize the expertise of teachers to share supervisory knowledge, skills and information					

C. Organization and Implementation of Instructional Supervision

Indicators	Strongly Agree	Agree	Moderately Agree	Dis-agree	Strongly Disagree
a. Lesson Plan Review					
<i>Instructional supervisor examines teacher's ...</i>					
1 formulation of behavioral learning objectives					
2 organization of RBEC/K-to-12 learning content					
3 utilization of innovative teaching strategies					
4 consumption of updated teaching references					
5 use of appropriate instructional devices					
6 preparation of meaningful learning experiences					
7 communication of higher order thinking skills					
8 construction of objective-oriented assessment					
9 application of learnt concept to real-life setting					
10 provision of skills-based enrichment					

b. Actual Classroom Observation					
<i>Instructional supervisor examines teacher's ...</i>					
1 preparation of functional lesson plans or appropriate daily logs					
2 implementation of RBEC/K-to-12 based curricular instruction or classroom lessons					
3 organization of classroom practices or teaching procedures					
4 establishment of classroom discipline and routine management					
5 accomplishment of school forms, teaching records, and learners' reports					

D. Dialogue and Discussion in Post-Instructional Supervision

Indicators	Strongly Agree	Agree	Moderately Agree	Dis-agree	Strongly Disagree
a. Immediacy of Feedback on Classroom Observation					
<i>Instructional supervisor ...</i>					
1 conducts supervisory conferences right after observing teachers					
2 provides immediate feedback after the teaching-learning process					
3 spends enough time to discuss teacher's strengths and capabilities					
4 gives sufficient time to discuss teacher's weaknesses and difficulties					
5 allots time to share supervisory experiences through constructive dialogue, mutual trust and shared expertise					
b. Adequacy of Feedback on Instructional Supervision					
<i>Instructional supervisor ...</i>					
1 provides data-based feedback and responses					
2 gives appreciation and positive comments					
3 discusses teacher's weaknesses and difficulties					
4 promotes two-way communication process					
5 supports curriculum and staff development					

E. Satisfaction with and Evaluation of Instructional Supervision

Indicators	Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Moderately Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Very Dissatisfied
1. Satisfaction with Instructional Supervision					
As a supervisee, I am satisfied with the following:					
a. Instructional Supervisory Practices based on the ...					
1 overall quality of instructional supervision					
2 general organization of instructional supervision					
3 administrative support to instructional supervision					
4 objective evaluation of instructional supervision					
5 cooperative action in instructional supervision					
b. Instructional Supervisor's ...					
1 planning skills on observing, monitoring and evaluating the instructional process					
2 analytical skills to explain the relationship that exist between teaching and learning					
3 social competence in building collaborative and empowering relationships					
4 communicative competence on holding one-on-one conferences with teachers					
5 creative and innovative skills in dealing with complex classroom practices					
2. Evaluation of Instructional Supervision					
a. Based on my observation, the instructional supervisor accomplishes the appraisal forms through:					
1 conducting lesson plan reviews					
2 performing classroom observations					
3 examining classroom discipline or management					
4 checking the routine management					
5 monitoring the record management					
b. Based on my observation, the instructional supervisor prepares the supervisory reports through:					
1 accomplishing the form 178 upon the observation of the teaching-learning process					
2 monitoring the class targets or accomplishments					
3 reviewing IPCRF as part of performance monitoring and tracking					
4 keeping the appraisal forms for record management and future reference					
5 assessing the realization of government's instructional policies and practices					

III. What is the teaching job performance of the teacher? _____

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